

weed species, wheat, barley, and maize were indexed by ELISA. The latex agglutination test was used to detect RTVs in wild rice.

Of 10 weed species, 3—*Ischaemum rugosum*, *Echinochloa crus-galli*, and *Leptochloa chinensis*—had only RTSV. No RTVs were detected from wheat and barley. Maize had only RTSV (Table 1).

Results of latex agglutination test showed that nine species of wild rice were infected with RTBV + RTSV (Table 2). *Oryza officinalis* had only RTBV; *O. eichingeri* had only RTSV. No virus was found in *O. ridleyi*. All lines of wild rice found in Thailand had RTBV + RTSV. ■

Table 1. Detection of RTBV and RTSV in extracts of weed species and cereal crops by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay.^a

Plant species	Inoculated plants (no.)	Plants (no.) infected with RTSV
<i>Chloris barbata</i>	57	0
<i>Digitaria adscendens</i>	54	0
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i>	49	1
<i>Echinochloa crus-galli</i>	36	2
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	36	2
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	23	0
<i>Jussiaea linifolia</i>	15	0
<i>Leersia hexandra</i>	5	0
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i>	15	0
<i>Fimbristylis milliacea</i>	5	0
<i>Zea maydis</i>	54	4
Wheat	180	0
Barley	180	0

^aExtract that gave yellow color in a well compared with extract of an uninoculated plant of the same species was considered positive in ELISA.

Table 2. Detection of RTV-associated virus in extracts of wild rice by latex agglutination test.

Entry	Inoculated plants (no.)	Infected plants ^a (no.)		
		RTBV	RTSV	RTBV+RTSV
<i>O. nivara</i>	17	3	0	14
<i>O. barthii</i>	12	0	6	4
<i>O. gluberrima</i>	31	4	8	7
<i>O. rufipogon</i>	34	26	6	38
<i>O. punctata</i>	33	3	5	6
<i>O. minuta</i>	35	4	8	6
<i>O. perennis</i>	10	3	0	4
<i>O. eichingeri</i>	12	0	3	0
<i>O. officinalis</i>	15	1	0	0
<i>O. ridleyi</i>	6	0	0	0
<i>P. nivara/O. sativa</i>	17	3	3	3
<i>O. sativa/O. spontanea</i>	26	1	4	6
TN1 (check)	53	3	11	35
Ayy-82-35	20	11	0	9
Ayy-82-36	25	0	0	25
Ayy-82-37	19	2	11	5
Ayy-82-38	10	4	2	3
Ayy-82-39	17	3	4	9
SRB-82-44	26	1	3	20
PSL-82-47	26	5	12	9
PSL-82-48	30	0	12	18
PSL-82-49	28	0	3	24
PSL-82-50	4	2	0	2
PSL-82-52	26	0	1	25
PSL-82-53	35	0	15	8
PSL-82-54	18	0	1	17
SPR-83-113	9	0	4	4
SRB-83-114	16	0	5	11
SRB-83-115	7	0	0	6
SRB-83-116	4	0	0	4
SRB-83-117	19	1	7	11
SRB-83-118	8	1	3	4
SPR-83-119	14	1	6	6
SPR-83-120	10	0	8	2
SPR-83-121-2	5	3	1	1
SPR-83-122	18	0	2	16
SRB-83-141	4	0	0	4
SRB-83-142	10	0	0	10
SRB-83-143	8	0	1	1
SRB-83-144	17	0	11	5

^aTest samples that showed clumping under the microscope compared with uninoculated samples were considered positive.

Integrated pest management— insects

Dynamics of major predator and prey species in ricefields

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We studied populations of important predator and prey species at five rice-growing sites in the Philippines. All arthropods inside a mylar enclosure (0.5 x 0.5 x 0.9 m) were sucked up using the FARMCOP suction device, with 10 samples/site. A total of 540 samples taken at weekly intervals were obtained, sorted into species, and identified.

Three species of Cicadellidae and two of Delphacidae accounted for most of the phytophagous Homoptera (Table 1). Two main groups of predators—Heteroptera and Araneae—were recorded. The three Heteroptera families were represented by one species each: *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, *Microvelia atrolineata*, and *Mesovelia vittigera*. Of 13 spider species, *Pardosa* (= *Lycosa*) *pseudoannulata*, three species of *Tetragnatha*, and members of family Linyphiidae were dominant.

The counts of delphacids and cicadellids in each sample were aggregated and the linear relationships with *C. lividipennis* (Miridae), spiders, and veliids + mesoveliids determined. Correlations ($p < 0.005$) were significant and positive in all cases. Regression coefficients are shown in Table 2.

High positive correlations or numerical responses to hopper density indicate that densities of the three groups of predators were directly related to hopper densities. *C. lividipennis* had strong numerical responses in Bayombong and Kiangan, but were negligible in IRRRI, Cabanatuan, and Banaue. Because *C. lividipennis* is a predator of hopper eggs, a delayed instead of a direct numerical response may be expected.

For spiders, responses were high in Kiangan, IRRRI, and Bayombong, but significantly lower in Cabanatuan and

Table 1. Proportion of major species in the arthropod guilds collected in 5 rice cultivation sites in the Philippines, 1989.

	Proportion (%)				
	IRRI (Laguna)	Cabanatuan, Nueva Ecija	Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya	Mountain Province	
				Kiangan	Banaue
Phytophages					
Hornoptera					
Cicadellidae	44.9	84.6	69.1	40.6	68.0
<i>N. virescens</i>	63.7	77.1	74.1	56.3	75.1
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	22.1	13.7	14.1	12.3	19.3
<i>R. dorsalis</i>	2.5	8.3	8.9	29.0	2.3
Delphacidae	55.1	15.4	30.9	59.4	32.0
<i>N. lugens</i>	27.8	28.7	49.0	25.3	25.1
<i>S. furcifera</i>	57.8	70.5	46.5	72.6	74.7
Diptera					
Ephydriidae	2.4	52.3	48.8	45.5	38.2
<i>H. philippina</i>	7.5	49.7	6.7	67.0	28.8
<i>N. spinosa</i>	50.3	10.7	4.6	13.6	19.3
<i>Psilopa</i> sp.		11.2	70.5	13.99	11.8
Chironomidae	4.5	36.5	31.3	49.8	60.2
<i>Chironomus</i> sp.1	0.0	100.0	100.0	99.8	2.5
<i>Chimnomus</i> sp.2	82.1	0	0.0	0.0	0.8
<i>Chironomus</i> sp.3	10.1	0	0.0	0.0	88.8
<i>Cryptochironomus</i> sp.	5.3	0	0.0	0.0	7.9
Phoridae	42.5	2.5	0.0	0.0	0.9
Sciomyzidae	42.8	2.5	8.2	1.1	0.2
Agromyzidae	0.0	6.2	11.8	3.6	0.5
Predators					
Heteroptera					
Miridae	3.0	4.3	10.7	27.4	29.2
Veliidae	90.6	95.5	82.2	62.2	29.7
Mesoveliidae	6.4	0.1	7.0	10.5	41.0
Araneae					
Lycosidae	39.8	33.0	24.4	43.8	54.1
Tetragnathidae	16.8	22.2	41.7	37.7	34.1
<i>Dyschiriognatha</i>	41.4	4.5	7.5	2.4	3.0
<i>T. maxillosa</i>	26.1	47.8	31.9	45.5	36.4
<i>T. javana</i>	29.1	23.4	12.8	17.1	24.2
<i>T. virescens</i>	3.4	24.3	47.8	35.0	36.4
Linyphiidae	39.7	35.1	23.0	9.1	6.9

Table 2. Linear regression coefficients^a of relationships between abundance of plants and leafhoppers and associated predators at different sites^b in the Philippines.

	Linear regression coefficient				
	IRRI (90)	Cabanatuan (80)	Bayombong (110)	Kiangan (100)	Banaue (130)
<i>Cyrtorhinus</i>	0.02 ± 0.01	0.03 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.03	0.48 ± 0.05	0.11 ± 0.01
Spiders	0.34 ± 0.04	0.14 ± 0.05	0.34 ± 0.05	0.54 ± 0.09	0.12 ± 0.01
Veliids and mesoveliids	0.29 ± 0.14	0.73 ± 0.25	0.54 ± 0.23	0.57 ± 0.13	0.26 ± 0.02

^a ±SEs. ^b In all occasions, data fitted the linear model, $y = mx + C$ at probability $p < 0.005$. Numbers in parentheses under each site indicate number of observations.

Banaue. Strong positive correlations for veliids and mesoveliids were obtained at all sites. Because spiders constitute a large proportion of all predators and their relative biomass is likely to be larger

than that of mirids and veliids, their impact may be greater than what the coefficients imply.

Predator-prey relationships appeared to be significantly lower in IRRI and

Banaue. These two sites had the highest and lowest predator-prey loads. Compared with Cabanatuan, Bayombong, and Kiangan, the two sites may be considered atypical of rice production areas: IRRI is an experimental farm with high diversity in plant stages and germplasm; Banaue has significantly lower median temperatures because of its elevation (1,524 m above sea level); Cabanatuan, Bayombong, and Kiangan are extensive rice cultivation areas. ■

Influence of lunar phase on green leafhopper (GLH) incidence

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We studied the influence of lunar phase on GLH attraction to light traps at RRS, Tirur, during 1987. A modified Robinson light trap, fitted with a 200-watt ordinary incandescent lamp, installed in the middle of ricefields was operated daily from 1800 to 0600 h. Daily collections were recorded during the 12 lunar cycles of 1987.

Three days on either side of the date of a new moon was taken as a new moon week and 3 d on either side of a full moon day constituted a full moon week. In-between periods formed the last and first quarter moon weeks.

Table 1. Effect of lunar cycle on population dynamics of rice GLH. RRS, Tirur, 1987.

Lunar cycle no.	Period	Mean incidence	
		Actual no.	Transformed value (log x)
1	12 Jan-9 Feb	529.8	2.427
2	10 Feb-11 Mar	51.3	1.489
3	12 Mar-10 Apr	198.5	2.028
4	11 Apr-9 May	574.3	2.465
5	10 May-7 Jun	9.53	1.932
6	8 Jun-7 Jul	329.8	2.425
7	8 Jul-5 Aug	1124.0	3.047
8	6 Aug-3 Sep	6379.8	3.437
9	4 Sep-3 Oct	722.0	2.356
10	4 Oct-1 Nov	83.5	1.826
11	2 Nov-1 Dec	931.3	2.688
12	2 Dec-30 Dec	2526.5	3.208
	LSD		0.589